

GETTING STUDENTS INTERESTED IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: This in the article education in institutions study taking of students foreign from the language received knowledge in strengthening applied innovative of technologies apply styles analysis done. Foreign language different methods with to teach the most important from events one as analysis does.

Key words: foreign language, information technology, innovative technology, technological tools, methods, methods

Current globalization period innovative education technologies and their pedagogical basics learned, study in the process modern-interactive teaching methods efficient use ways research reach today's of the day current problems one being remains. To education innovative of approach socio-pedagogical necessity the following with measured by:

1. Science and technology development and socio-economic update continuously education system, in particular, education in institutions study process advanced foreign experiences learning, education innovative approaches and information from technologies used without improvement;
2. In elementary school and youth informativeness level, intellectual potential, social activity, creativity skills to develop service doer to the individual directed of teaching efficient organizational forms, technologies Create and to practice app reach;
3. Pedagogical innovations mastery and him app to do relatively of the teacher professional-innovative competence development necessity;

Our country to independence after reaching. their languages to study demand that is and interest increased. Young students for many opportunities by creating given. Education. in the process modern information from technologies fruitful use and education to the process modern innovative technologies take access through education quality and efficiency is increasing. In particular, abroad language in learning such information and communication from technologies of use one how much advantages there is Language study and in teaching innovative technologies are very important have Technological from tools use foreign language of learning each one hand in aspect

(reading, writing, listening, speaking). will come for example, listening to understand for, of course without computer, player, CD discs this the process done increase possible not.

Education in the process modern from technologies in use Students are also information - communicative technologies good to know and of them use take important factor is considered Foreign language modern from technologies using teach and learning the most Samador of methods is one

It is known that the lesson different different games based on passing of student's opportunities demonstration attention summation, knowledge and skills increase and strong to be provides. Game technology in use of the student himself manifestation to do in life stable place to find himself management, own opportunities done increase fundamental needs relies on Any play at the core common acceptance done education principles, tactics lie down need Study to the games study subject's basis by doing taken need Games in the process student simple to class than this to training more interesting approaches and easily activity shows. Highlight must be a game the most avallo, of teaching one is a method. Students _ playful to lessons interested participate, win to win they strive, teacher they are through to the student also provides education. A student English game play and talk I can listen understand when I can, write He believes that he can take it, he is interested.

Current period of our country all in the fields , that's it including the people education done in the system being increased wide extensive changes all pedagogues forward of the student knowledge high level increase _ independent their thinking _ vital activity development ; high moral adjectives educate ; thinking , communication , study , work to do was abilities progressive carry on such as complicated and responsible tasks is putting Each child only _ to himself special to know activity , will , character , behavior features have _ At school education to give that 's it in the process features to know and based on that treating them individually to be it is necessary That's it account only when received one pedagogue his own main task , that is young to generation education to give work successful done increases .

Initial class reading the lessons are the same so in forms organize is being done. A student the text right , fast , understanding reading , content appropriation is the first with reading in their classes face will come Reading in their classes to the children State education standard requirements according to acquisitions need was knowledge is given Initial class reading in textbooks given topics scope much wide they are _ mother nature , year seasons , people oral creativity , work love is the main thing holiday dates ,

independence , homeland , spirituality such as common topics within combined . Reading to classes competence the approach current reach information and advanced pedagogical from technologies use education in the content to himself special and student from the person to himself suitable competence forms. Advanced pedagogical technologies based on new knowledge education to the content suitable way modern in the spirit absorption, pedagogical technology education to the system wide current to achieve, perfect a person reached education, education system quality in terms of Entirely new to stage raise today's of the day current is the issue.

Current in the day of world multimedia technologies development as a result surface coming each different activity types of computerization new to the stage witness is happening. Graphics , animation , photo , video, sound , text interactive respectively whole information environment creates , in which user quality in terms of new to opportunities have will be Multimedia technologies the most wide application education in the field - university from classes home _ _ conditions until there is Multimedia products different different information , demonstration and advertising purposes successful used in telecommunications of multimedia current to be done new of programs fast paces with to growth impulse gave _ Especially education _ to the process multimedia take access present of the day current issues in turn enters.

Multimedia technologies study processes current reach education information important from the points is one Current multimedia technologies at the time information of technologies the fastest developing and promising directions one is considered This is multimedia unique information to the user in the environment organize done new data with to work possibility hardware and _ software tools is a set. Computer technologies today's in the day many students of life indispensable to the part became _ They , often , them simple school from the textbook according to more interest with acceptance they do Current at the time a lot education on the gallows the following you will find possible : voice to write and increase tools (electrophones , tape recorders , CD- players), systems and telephone , telegraph and radio communication tools (phones , facsimile devices , teletypes , telephone stations , radio communication systems), systems and television , radio broadcasting means (television and radio reception doers , training television and radio, DVD - players), optical and projection cinema and photographic equipment (cameras , films , projectors , film projectors), printing release , copy and another documents information reproduce (printers , copy transfer devices), data electron in the form demonstration reach , re work and storage opportunity provider computer tools (computers , printers , scanners

, plotters), communication channels (modems , wired , artificial satellite , optical through fiber , radio relay) . information transmission provider telecommunications systems and another channel types information transmission for intended communication).

Education _ quality increase for technical tools : audio-video, film materials , computers , video projector , slides , art from the works fragments ; modern pedagogical technologies , in particular interactive of the methods appropriate using they are coming Innovative education _ technologies education quality improve efficiency _ increase , teacher , student as well as the team in the middle mutually cooperation decision finding , ideological and spiritual to unity achieve , strive towards a single goal , har one education of the recipient internal opportunities come true issue , person as manifestation to be for necessary conditions and environment in creating big to opportunities have.

Summary by doing in other words, English language in their classes innovative methods to apply as a result of students makes sense and critical thinking abilities develops, speech smooth, fast and right answer to give qualification is formed. Such methods in the student to knowledge passion wakes up. A student to lessons thorough readiness to see strives _ And this the student's education of the process active subjects turns _

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